

SKILLS AND LEARNING STATEMENT

For Research and Analysis Project

Word count: 1924
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Question One: Reflect on what you have learnt from the meetings with your project mentor, including the presentation that you have to your project mentor?

Meeting 1:

The thought of attempting for OBU was quite overwhelming for me. So, after a lot of thought when I finally decided to do this project, I met my mentor. I was quite sceptical if I would be able to successfully complete this project as I had absolutely no idea how an analytical project like this is supposed to be done. Hence, with a million thoughts and anxiety running through my veins, I finally attended the meeting unsure of whether I would take up this project. But, to my surprise, by the end of this meeting, I knew I was capable enough to do this project with the help of the knowledge that I had acquired during my ACCA studies.

The mentor boosted my confidence enough that I was able to decide on the topic I would like to pursue my project towards. Once I decided the topic, we had a thorough discussion about why I would like to take up Toyota as my research company after which I shared my project title, initial outline and RAP objectives. I was also suggested to start my SLS along with the rest of the project.

Then, in the next section of the meeting, we discussed the method of writing which he suggested should be formal and passive in order to present it more professional. He also helped me understand that "Quality over Quantity" is vital while also not to forget to tag the reference of the information obtained.

The company that I had chosen was extensive in nature and hence, it was quite possible for me to drift away from the topic and end up losing time in gathering information that was not necessary. Here, my mentor played an important role in helping me understand how to structure and divide the project in order to manage my time efficiently and effectively.

Meeting 2:

After completing the first draft of my project, I had a meeting with my mentor in which he did a critical analysis of the study I had done and it was an eye opener. He pointed out a lot of mistakes which I had committed with regards to referencing and the analysis I had done on the ratios. I was facing trouble with this analysis and to draw conclusions as the academics' dummy companies and real life companies vary massively. I must admit, it was a daunting task.

He also helped me sort the extensive data as I was struggling to keep up with the word limit without compromising on the necessary information. He suggested that I should focus more on the analysis than just mere description of the movement of the figures illustrated in the charts.

As both Toyota and Honda are foreign companies, I did not get a chance to interview any of their personnel or to access any of the first-hand information. I had to solely rely on the information that was available on the internet and hence, I was not quite satisfied with the reliability of the information obtained as a lot of websites contradicted each other. When I discussed my concern with the mentor, He suggested a few reliable sources to cross check and change the information if need be.

Meeting 3:

This was our final meeting where all the sections of the project were discussed and I was allowed to present it to the mentor. This presentation allowed me to gain confidence in the project as the mentor questioned and cross-questioned me about the various conclusions and recommendations I had drawn. My mentor suggested me to make some necessary formatting which is extremely important for a good presentation. I was happy by the end that I had learnt so much during the course of this project and I thanked my mentor for being with me through this journey and making a seemingly impossible task possible for me.

Question 2: To what extent do you think you have achieved the RAP research objectives you set?

According to me, I have answered the project in the best possible manner keeping the limitations of provided. The word limit was the main constraint I had to keep in mind.

To analyse Toyota Motor Corp.'s business and financial performance, I did a Horizontal Analysis to compare theirs and their competitor's year-by-year performance, I did an in-depth ratio analysis, I used PEST and SWOT model for analysing the business performance. These analyses give a decent picture of Toyota but since it is a humungous company with billions of dollars involved, few more tools like Porter's Diamond Model or MOST analysis would have given a deeper analysis of their performance as they have a huge contribution not only in the economic sustainability but also in environmental sustainability as well but due to limited words I was unable to do so.

The data available on Toyota is immense as it is a key player of the automobile industry. In the beginning I faced a lot of troubles choosing which information would be most relevant and specific to my project and relating that information to the specific areas of my research was a difficult task. Initially I had extracted most of the data from Toyota's Annual report as it had most of the information I required, later my mentor suggested that the information there might be biased, so it would not be wise to take everything from it, it would be like presenting the Annual report itself. So I extracted information from other sources as well and compared them with the annual report to identify the inconsistencies between them.

I wanted an external look for my project so I had shown my project to my teachers and colleagues who suggested me how I could enhance it. The Annual reports of Toyota were very

informative and precise which enabled me to obtain necessary information for ratios. However I could not obtain much information externally about some of the ratios such as creditor days and debtor days. If I was allowed some more word limit, I could also add important ratios such as asset turnover, price-to-book ratio as well.

However, even with the limitations I have mentioned above, I tried my best to extract best possible data for completing my report and my research objectives.

Question 3: How have you demonstrated your interpersonal and communication skills during the project work?

Since I have not done any project of this kind, I did not read articles or news to this depth, during the course I read a lot of them which developed my reading skills. I had to demonstrate interpersonal and communication skills from the very beginning of this project. At first, I did not know the kind of language that is supposed to be used when trying to put across the information for the evaluator. The writing skills that I had developed over the course of ACCA were not sufficient enough for me to be confident enough to frame my sentences as the approach that we use in RAP is quite different from the language that we use in our Exam papers.

After a lot of reading that I did online, I finally understood the method to be used while doing an analytic project such as this. I was required to be quite consistent with my language and the information that I present should be relevant while also being mindful of the word limit constraint put. So this research helped me develop my vocabulary extensively.

As I did this project in the time when COVID-19 was spread and everyone was maintaining social distancing, so I had online sessions with my mentor and could not meet him in person, circumstances demanded that I rely on social media and technology to contact my mentor. This was quite challenging at first as I had to build a rapport with my mentor in order to understand what he is trying to convey and vice versa. But, as we went along this project, communication became easier and more convenient as we developed an understanding between us.

During the course of this project, I also learnt how to skim through the information provided without wasting too much time on irrelevant information available hence, helping me with time-management. As both Toyota and Honda are vast global companies, the information available online was massive and I learnt how to sift through the information and pick out only those that would be beneficial for my project.

Finally, when it was time to present the project to my mentor, I had to pre-plan my presentation as it was a virtual meeting and I had to be as precise and concise as possible in order to put across the information needed without causing too much confusion. Hence, this gave me a lot of confidence that in the real-life scenario where I would be required to address a large group, I will be in a position to present and communicate in a manner expected from a professional.

Question 4: Explain on how undertaking the RAP helped you in your accountancy studies and/or current employment role?

Being an ACCA pursuant and a seeker for a career in finance, RAP allowed me to widen my knowledge spectrum immensely. The outlook that I had towards finance and accountancy was quite different from what I have now. This is because, in the examination or the examples that we solve in our academics are quite different in nature as compared to the real word scenarios. I realised that the information that is provided to us in our examination is all the necessary information that is required for us to do an analysis. Whereas, during RAP I understood that a real life scenario requires us to be more analytical in nature and also to be more attentive to details and smart to gather necessary information from reliable sources.

The extensive reading that I did, helped me understand the automobile industry better while simultaneously develop my report writing skills. I learnt how to analyse the financial and non-financial data and draw conclusions from them. I also had the chance to look into the Japanese laws and regulations which was all new to me.

The analysis of fictional companies provided in the examinations and a real company is extremely different. This was a whole new experience for me as I had never been through any financial statements of a real company. The actual company information is massive so it becomes a bit difficult to conclude about the company.

I learnt how to make and present a presentation which I had never done before. This skill that I acquired through RAP will be extremely beneficial when I start my career as an ACCA. I also learnt about citation and referencing which will be very beneficial in the future. Time-management was an important area that I realised that I have to work on as I was quite over-confident and delayed my deadlines which in-turn affected my milestones.

Thereby, I can conclude by saying that, with the experience and knowledge that I gained through RAP, I will be in a better position now for my next assignment which I think would not have been possible if I had not decided to take it up.